

Greenhouse gas and acid gases **conversion** by electrothermal catalysis

Utilization of H₂S and CO₂ for production of industrially valuable carbon monoxide and sulphur

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PROJECT INFORMATION:

Project coordinator:
Ghent University

Duration: 09.2022 - 02.2026

Total budget:
€ 7 681 307, 50

EU contribution:
€ 7 022 265,00

SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNOLOGICAL OBJECTIVES

- 🔌 Development of **stable** and **sulphur-resistant catalysts** and construction of a **pilot-scale reactor** to demonstrate the conversion of CO₂ and H₂S into COS;
- 🔌 Validation of the quality of the reaction products and conversion of CO into **green methanol**;
- 🔌 Construction of reactor and process models with integrated microkinetics for process optimization and scale-up;
- 🔌 Demonstration of the techno-economic and environmental performance of developed **e-CODUCT reactors** and models via extensive techno-economic evaluation and LCA modeling.

Figure: e-CODUCT process.

